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BARRIERS CONTRIBUTING TO WOMEN UNDERREPRESENTATION IN DECISION-MAKING POSITIONS IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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Abstract

Women play a crucial role in society, as their status contributes significantly to its progress. However, in numerous societies that adhere to patriarchal norms, women frequently face the perception of being subordinate to men, leading to their marginalisation from esteemed and practical roles that are exclusively reserved for males. The lack of female presence in high-level management roles in educational institutions remains a significant issue that is not limited to specific regions but is rather a prevalent issue worldwide. Therefore, this study presents a comprehensive systematic review that explores the barriers influencing women's participation in decision-making. This process involved analysing data from scholarly databases such as Google Scholar and Scopus such as peer-reviewed journals and previously conducted research papers on the relevant keywords (women in academia, decision making, barriers contributing to gender inequality in education, and higher education leadership). The results revealed that women's participation in decision-making is influenced by a complex interplay of individual, socio-cultural, and structural factors. These factors include cultural norms, gender stereotypes, lack of access to education and resources, discriminatory practices, and limited representation in decision-making positions. Based on the findings, several recommendations are proposed to enhance women's participation in decision-making in South Africa. These recommendations include the need for targeted interventions to address gender inequalities, promoting women's empowerment through education and skills development, and creating inclusive policies and legislation.

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Additionally, it is crucial to raise awareness and challenge societal norms and attitudes that perpetuate gender disparities.

Keywords: *Women, participation in decision making, barriers, feminist theory, higher education setting, South Africa context*

1. Introduction

Women play a crucial role in society, as their status contributes significantly to its progress (Kapur, 2019). However, in numerous societies that adhere to patriarchal norms, women frequently face the perception of being subordinate to men, leading to their marginalisation from esteemed and practical roles that are exclusively reserved for males (Alemu, 2012). This marginalisation encompasses positions in property management, leadership roles in various domains of society such as religion and governance, and education. As highlighted by Alemu (2012), this societal structure perpetuates gender inequality and restricts women's access to opportunities for growth and advancement. Consequently, women are often denied the chance to contribute their skills and expertise in influential positions, hindering their overall participation in decision-making in matters that concern them. Participation in decision-making is described by Ngo Ndjama (2024) as the active involvement of staff in a company's efforts to carry out its mission statement and uphold its fundamental values by contributing their ideas, skills, and initiatives to problem-solving and decision-making. Hora (2014:102) explains that "A woman is an adult female human being, as contrasted to men, an adult male, and a girl, a female child. The term woman (irregular plural: women) is used to indicate biological sex distinctions, cultural gender role distinctions, or both". The level of women's involvement in decision-making roles remains significantly low, despite their significant contributions to their households, food production systems, and national economies (Kavita, 2012). Moreover, Kavita (2012) argues that this can be attributed to a range of factors that influence women's participation in decision-making, including demographic, educational, cultural, and inherent abilities of women. Herri, Maarty and Handika (2016) point out that the lack of women on corporate boards is detrimental to companies, as it limits their access to a diverse pool of talent. Herri et al. (2016) add that companies with a significant presence of women in board and top management positions tend to outperform those without, and having gender-diverse boards positively affects overall performance.

2. Problem statement

The gender issue of women's participation in decision-making roles has garnered significant attention (Munemo, 2017). Likewise, Alemu (2012) emphasised that the promotion of women's involvement in all aspects of life has emerged as a significant concern in discussions about development. The issue of gender equality in higher education institutions persists due to the sluggish and unequal progress of women's entry as both students and employees, underscoring a significant problem (Sifuna, 2006). In the same way, Ademe and Singh (2015) argue that women are significantly underrepresented across all educational levels, with tertiary education being particularly affected. Herri et al. (2016) underscore that the lack of female presence in high-level management roles in educational institutions remains a significant issue. Gallant (2014) adds that the lack of female representation in decision-making positions within higher education is not limited to specific regions, but rather a prevalent issue worldwide. In response to this issue, several countries started acknowledging the lack of gender diversity in decision-making positions within higher education institutions towards the end of the twentieth century (Ademe & Singh, 2015). However, despite the acknowledgement of gender disparities in higher education by numerous countries by the end of the 20th century, significant progress has not been made in addressing this issue (Xiang, Ingram & Cangemi, 2017). Consequently, women globally have endeavoured to organise and express their issues while striving to amplify their voices; nevertheless, women in Africa face numerous challenges in this pursuit (Kavita, 2012). Without the active participation of women in decision-making, socio-economic development cannot be effectively realised (Alemu, 2012).

A gap in research has been identified in the examination of barriers that lead to the under-representation of women in decision-making roles within higher education settings. This gap in the literature highlights the need for further investigation into the factors that hinder women from advancing to decision-making positions in academia. Previous studies have touched upon this issue, but there is still a lack of comprehensive understanding of the specific challenges and obstacles faced by women in higher education leadership roles (Adamu, 2023; Tsehay 2020; Xiang et al., 2017; Herri et al., 2016; Ademe & Singh, 2015; Hora, 2014; Alemu 2012 & Kavita, 201). However, it is important to note that the existing literature on this topic primarily focuses on studies conducted in Ethiopia and Kenya,

leaving a gap in the understanding of the situation in other regions or countries. This limited scope of research restricts the ability to develop comprehensive strategies and interventions to address the under-representation of women in decision-making positions in higher education institutions globally. By addressing this research gap, scholars can contribute to the development of strategies and policies aimed at promoting gender equality and diversity in academic decision-making positions.

The following questions are developed for this study:

2.1 To what extent do personal barriers influence women's participation in decision-making roles in higher education in South Africa?

2.2 How do socio-cultural barriers impact women's participation in decision-making roles in higher education in South Africa?

2.3 To what extent do institutional barriers affect women's participation in decision-making roles in higher education in South Africa?

3. Significance of the study

Adamu (2023) posits that the roles of decision-making in higher education are not limited to a specific gender and are not exclusively assigned to men. Nevertheless, Adamu (2023) emphasises that numerous studies and real-world examples indicate that women are significantly underrepresented in these positions within higher education globally. It is crucial to recognise that the exclusion of women from decision-making roles not only perpetuates gender inequality but also hampers the diversity of perspectives and experiences necessary for effective decision-making in academia. The factors contributing to this imbalance encompass deeply ingrained gender biases, stereotypes, and discriminatory practices that hinder women's progress and limit their access to decision-making roles. Thus, this research holds significance as it corresponds to Sustainable Development Goal 5 (SDG), which strives to advance gender equality, empower women, and foster their active participation and equitable opportunities for leadership in all areas of politics, economics, and public life. The United Nations (UN) underscores that gender equality is not only a fundamental human right but also a vital component for the establishment of a harmonious, prosperous, and sustainable global society (UN, 2022). This study delves deeper into the specific aspects and implications of gender equality and its multifaceted impact on different higher

education institutions in Africa and abroad, thereby contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of this crucial issue. It presents a comprehensive understanding of the specific strategies, policies, and initiatives that can be implemented to promote gender equality, empower women, and create an inclusive environment that fosters their leadership potential. Additionally, this research shed light on the challenges and barriers that hinder women's contribution to decision-making positions, allowing researchers to devise effective solutions and interventions to overcome these obstacles. Ultimately, this study contributes to the broader discourse on gender equality and serves as a catalyst for positive change towards a more equitable and just world.

Furthermore, participation is an approach to development that acknowledges the importance of including marginalised groups in the creation and execution of policies that affect their well-being (Alemu, 2012). This inclusive approach aims to empower and give voice to those who have been historically excluded or disadvantaged, ensuring that their perspectives, needs, and aspirations are taken into account. By actively engaging marginalised communities in this instance women in decision-making processes, participation seeks to address the systemic inequalities and power imbalances that perpetuate their marginalisation. It recognises that sustainable development can only be achieved when all individuals have equal opportunities to contribute, benefit, and shape the policies that shape their lives.

4. Literature review

4.1 Theoretical framework

The feminist theory provides a framework through which the participation of women in decision-making roles in higher education can be understood. In the same way, Ademe and Singh (2015) commented that the research on women's participation in decision-making relies on feminist theory, which acknowledges the extensive impact of gender divisions on society and aims to comprehend the marginalisation of women and the societal structures that perpetuate their subjugation and subordination. Usmani, Ali, Kottaparamban, Hadi (2023) explain that despite the significant advancements made globally, the issue of gender inequality persists across various societies. Gender disparities can be witnessed in numerous areas, including workplace bias towards women, instances of sexual harassment, and limited educational opportunities. Feminist theories

play a crucial role in empowering women to combat such discrimination and strive for equality (Usmani et al., 2023). It emphasises the importance of challenging traditional gender norms and power structures that have historically marginalised women in decision-making positions within academia. By examining how gender inequality operates within educational institutions, feminist theory sheds light on the barriers that women face in accessing and advancing in decision-making roles. Likewise, by examining the numerous similarities between genders, the feminist perspective asserts that both women and men possess equal potential for personal growth and development (Ademe & Singh, 2015). However, at the policy level, Ilesanmi (2018) observes that feminist theorists suggest that it is crucial to include women as a unified group in discussions that lead to policy-making and implementation. This is because they have distinct and diverse experiences that differ from those of men. Consequently, it is essential to have them represented in institutions to effectively articulate their unique interests and ensure their needs are addressed (Ilesanmi, 2018).

Furthermore, feminist theory highlights the need for systemic change to address these barriers and promote gender equity in higher education leadership. Tsehay (2020) explains that women's participation in their institution's life, as proposed by feminist theory, serves as a means to challenge the patriarchal systems that limit the effective use of women's abilities for transformative change. It also emphasises the importance of including women fully and enabling their active participation in crucial decision-making processes to establish and achieve gender equality and democratic goals (Tsehay, 2020). This includes advocating for policies and practices that support the recruitment, retention, and advancement of women in decision-making roles, as well as challenging discriminatory practices and attitudes that perpetuate gender inequality. By applying a feminist lens to the study of women's participation in higher education leadership, researchers and policymakers can develop strategies to promote greater gender diversity and inclusivity in decision-making processes in higher education settings. Thus, this theory provides a framework for understanding and identifying the systemic barriers that hinder gender diversity and promote a more inclusive society.

4.2 Women and decision-making

According to Tsehay (2020), the field of decision-making has been extensively studied due to its profound influence on organisations

and society as a whole. Koziol-Nadolna and Beyer (2021) note that managers play a crucial role in resource management by making decisions that impact short- and long-term goals, as well as determining the success or failure of a venture. This activity is essential for organisations daily, with the accuracy of decisions serving as a key measure of a manager's performance (Koziol-Nadolna & Beyer, 2021). Decision-making entails the selection of one option from multiple alternatives to fulfil a specific purpose, making it a crucial task for managers (Tsehay, 2020). Gorgulho, Tavares, Pascoa and Tribolet (2015) argue that the process of decision-making consists of eight stages namely problem definition, requirement determination, goal establishment, alternative identification, criteria definition, decision-making tool selection, alternative evaluation, and solution validation as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Decision-Making Process (Gorgulho et al., 2015)

Based on Figure 1, the first stage is problem definition, where the decision-maker identifies the issue at hand that requires a decision to be made (Birt, 2022). Following this, requirement determination involves understanding the necessary conditions or constraints that need to be considered in the decision-making process (Koziol-Nadolna & Beyer, 2021). Goal establishment is crucial as it sets the direction and purpose of the decision, guiding the decision-maker towards a specific outcome. Alternative identification is the stage where different options or choices are brainstormed and considered as potential solutions to the problem. Criteria definition involves establishing the factors or standards that will be used to evaluate the alternatives and make a decision (Taherdoost & Madanchian, 2023). Selecting the appropriate decision-making tool is essential as it provides a structured approach to analysing and comparing the alternatives based on the established criteria. Before reaching conclusions in decision-making, it is essential to select the correct

alternative; it is a crucial procedure that relies on relevant information to yield the intended results. Alternative evaluation is the stage where each option is assessed against the criteria to determine its feasibility and effectiveness in addressing the problem. Finally, solution validation ensures that the chosen alternative is validated through testing or analysis to confirm its viability and potential success (Taherdoost & Madanchian, 2023). In summary, women's participation in decision-making entails their active involvement in the creation and implementation of decisions that impact organisations or institutions (Ilesanmi, 2018).

The involvement of women in higher education has seen a significant rise, particularly in roles as faculty members and support staff in academic institutions (Mohajeri, Mokhtar, & Balash, 2015). However, Herri et al. (2016) revealed that research findings are still indicating an imbalance in gender representation within top administrative roles, revealing a disparity where women are underrepresented compared to men. Munemo (2017) is of the view that in Africa and other developing countries, women face various obstacles that hinder their participation in decision-making, such as limited access to education, cultural norms, structural barriers, inadequate resources, and societal expectations that assign caregiving roles to women. Xiang et al. (2017) add that despite acknowledging gender disparities in higher education towards the end of the 20th century, significant progress in addressing this issue has not been made. Ademe and Singh (2015) underscore that the most pronounced disparity between genders is observed in higher education, which plays a crucial role in shaping women's involvement in the workforce at a professional level and their impact on public policy and practice. Herri et al. (2016) add that despite advancements in education and academic qualifications among women, their participation in decision-making positions within faculty and university management remains limited, resulting in their exclusion from decision-making processes. Over time, men have maintained authority in making decisions, establishing laws, and formulating policies across both public and private domains (Tsehay, 2020). Xiang et al. (2017) emphasise that the lack of female representation in decision-making positions within higher education is not limited to specific regions, but rather a prevalent issue on a global scale. Tsehay (2020) compliments that the discrimination against women persists in various countries, despite their involvement in public administration and decision-making.

Women's roles in decision-making have been crucial in shaping societies across the globe, highlighting the important contributions women have made throughout history (Hora, 2014). Therefore, Hora (2014) advocates that various literary works have documented the fact that although women were often excluded from holding formal decision-making positions, they have consistently played significant roles in both times of conflict and peace as community organizers and activists (Hora, 2014). The rationale behind advocating for women's participation in decision-making and leadership stems from the belief that all individuals are entitled to partake in choices that shape their own lives. This principle forms the basis of striving for equal participation in decision-making between genders, emphasising that women, being most familiar with their circumstances, should have an equal say alongside men to ensure their viewpoints are adequately considered across all decision-making realms, ranging from personal to societal, local to international (Miranda, 2005). To ensure the successful implementation of policies that impact the broader population, it is essential to have equal representation of both men and women in decision-making processes. However, progress towards achieving gender parity in managerial roles for women has been sluggish and inconsistent (Kavita, 2012). As a result, women face significant challenges in progressing professionally and engaging in decision-making within higher education institutions. Nevertheless, Herri et al. (2016) are of the opinion that increasing the representation of women with their distinct leadership styles in middle management or senior roles within higher education institutions is anticipated to enhance the overall performance and productivity of universities and the quality of decisions.

4.3 Higher education institutions

Nyoni and He (2019) explain that higher education typically refers to education at the university level, encompassing various qualifications like higher national diplomas, foundation degrees, honours degrees, and advanced programs including master's degrees and doctorates. Globally, these are acknowledged as symbols of specialised knowledge accompanied by a diverse set of abilities highly valued by employers. In the context of this research, higher education simply pertains to the university level (Nyoni & He, 2019). It plays a crucial role in fostering economic and social progress by providing individuals with the necessary knowledge and skills to enhance their productivity and contribute to national growth and competitiveness

(Ademe & Singh, 2015). Wolhuter and Langa (2021) state that universities play a crucial role in society through six key points: initially, they serve as an establishment for education and knowledge acquisition; secondly, they are responsible for carrying out research activities; thirdly, they engage in various forms of service, such as faculty engagement and outreach programs; fourthly, they act as the moral compass of society by critiquing its norms and practices; fifthly, they have to uphold, preserve, and enhance cultural heritage; and lastly, they are tasked with fostering innovation and creativity within society. Universities play a crucial role in fostering competitive economies through their research, innovation, and development of highly skilled individuals. Additionally, they have a significant impact on democracy by promoting social critique, nurturing critical citizenship, and fostering a diverse intellectual culture (Wolhuter & Langa, 2021). Through access to education and resources for expanding and diversifying knowledge, individuals are empowered to make significant contributions to society and the economy (Ademe & Singh, 2015).

The University's management is composed of several key positions, including the Chancellor, Vice-Chancellor and Principal, Executive, Vice-Principals, Executive Directors, Registrar, Council, Senate, Faculties, departments, schools, and other academic structures determined by the Council (University of Pretoria, 2024). In the same vein, it is composed of the Chancellor of the University, the Principal and Vice-Chancellor and the Pro Vice-Chancellor (UNISA, 2006). The Management Committee assists the Principal and Vice-Chancellor in his day-to-day management of the University. This committee consists of the Principal and Vice-Chancellor, the Pro Vice-Chancellor, the Vice Principals and the Registrar (UNISA, 2006). Council is the highest authority of the University and has 30 members, of whom at least 60 per cent are not employees or students of the University. Likewise, De la Rey (2015) points out that higher education institutions, under the legislative framework, are considered juristic persons with the institution's Council serving as the governing body, comprising a maximum of 30 members. It is required that at least 60 percent of the Council members are individuals who are not affiliated with the institution either as employees or students (De la Rey, 2015). The Senate is responsible and accountable to the Council for the academic, research, tuition and community service activities of the University (University of Pretoria, 2024). As the highest authority on academic matters, the

Senate approves all academic programmes and matters related to tuition (UNISA, 2006). De la Rey (2015) states that the Council oversees governance while the Vice Chancellor and Executive team handle the management of the institution. Senates are in charge of academic affairs, focusing on teaching and research. For efficiency, the Council has the authority to delegate certain powers to the Vice Chancellor, who in turn can delegate to executive members, within the limits set by the Act (de la Rey, 2015). Additionally, there are various support services, offices, bodies, and structures as determined by the Council, as well as the Institutional Forum and Student Representative Council (University of Pretoria, 2024). The higher education sector must recognise the significance of increased female representation in decision-making positions and acknowledge the substantial impact of their progress on both the higher education sector and society as a whole, along with the various educational and financial advantages associated with higher education institutions.

5. Materials and methods

The study utilises a secondary data collection process to achieve the study's objectives as shown in Table 1. This process involves analysing data from scholarly databases such as Google Scholar and Scopus such as peer-reviewed journals and previously conducted research papers on the relevant keywords (women in academia, decision making, barriers contributing to gender inequality in education, and higher education leadership). Utilising a secondary data set provided the researcher with the opportunity to discover novel perspectives and gain fresh insights from existing research findings.

Table 1: Systematic literature review process

Process	Number of articles found	Number of articles discarded
Title screening	287	
Abstract screening		124
Full article screening Exclusion criteria: Secondary/high schools, Primary schools, Corporate/companies/organisations		151
Duplicate		4
Articles included		8

The systematic literature review process outlined in Table 1 provides a comprehensive overview of the stages involved in the selection of relevant articles for analysis. Initially, a total of 287 articles were identified during the title screening phase. Following this, the abstract screening phase resulted in the retention of 124 articles for further consideration. The subsequent full article screening phase applied specific exclusion criteria, which eliminated articles related to secondary and primary schools, as well as those pertaining to corporate entities and organisations, leading to the exclusion of 151 articles. Additionally, four duplicate articles were identified and discarded. Ultimately, this rigorous process culminated in the inclusion of eight articles that met all the necessary criteria for the review.

6. Findings

Analysing data that has already been collected, researchers delved into the subject matter and uncovered new patterns and trends that were not initially explored as presented in Table 2. This approach allowed for a more comprehensive understanding of the barriers contributing to the underrepresentation of women in decision-making

positions in higher education institutions and contributed to the advancement of knowledge.

Table 2: Literature overview of the barriers contributing to the underrepresentation of women in decision-making positions in higher education

Author & Year Country	Title of the article	Methodology	Key findings	Conclusion & Recommendations
Adamu (2023)	Barriers to Women's Participation in and Contribution to Leadership in Ethiopian Higher Education	The study used a phenomenological research design to better understand barriers to women's leadership development in higher education from the views and experiences of women leaders. Data were generated from 12 women vice presidents and official documents. The participant	The result revealed that institutional barriers are considered the greatest, as they also exacerbate sociocultural and personal barriers to women's leadership development.	The barriers to women's leadership are multifaceted and addressing these challenges requires a holistic approach and concerted efforts from major stakeholders, especially policymakers.

		s were drawn from each type and generation of universities that exist in Ethiopian higher education.		
Tsehay (2020) Ethiopia	Women in Decision-making: Investigating Roles and Challenges in Selected Governmental Offices at Hosanna City Administration	The study employed a qualitative method. Whereas participants of the study were selected purposively, data were collected through interviews and analysed thematically.	the overburden of women, low access to decision-making positions, backward socio-cultural attitudes and practices, feelings of discrimination, feelings of inefficacy and lack of motivation, low educational status and insufficient institutional support were the main challenges to women's decision-making activity	Therefore, appreciating women's role in decision-making activities and working to ease their challenges must be the timely actions of all concerned parties.
Nyoni & He	Barriers and	The study comprised	The findings showed the	The study demonstrate

<p>(2019) Tanzania</p>	<p>Biases: Under-Representation of Women in Top Leadership Positions in Higher Education in Tanzania</p>	<p>a sample of 250 respondents with the use of a case study research design constructed on the application of mixed methods (qualitative and quantitative). Thus, non-probability sampling was applied to qualitative data collection while probability sampling was used in quantitative data. qualitative (semi-structured interviews & focus group discussion) & quantitative method</p>	<p>fundamental relationship between individual, administrative and societal factors that block women from reaching the top decision-making positions in universities.</p>	<p>that gender mainstreaming is a system which can be connected to adjust the hierarchical structures, methods and culture and bring positive conditions which advance gender equality.</p>
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		(questionnaire).		
Xiang et al. (2017) USA, Europe, Mexico Australia New Zealand China	Barriers Contributing to Under-Representation of Women in High-level Decision-making Roles across Selected Countries	Systematic literature review	Traditional family roles, such as being wives and mothers. Gender stereotyping and discrimination Traditional culture, social, distinct practices and beliefs regarding traditions, education traditional ideologies	
Rizwana & Schmiede (2017) Tanzania	Barriers to women's underrepresentation in academic excellence and positions of power	Women employed across different levels of hierarchy, ranging from research assistants to professors or decision-making roles, were included in the study. Four types of	There were several barriers which women experienced in academia ranging from personal, organisational or hierarchical to societal	There are various factors contributing to the underrepresentation of women in higher education decision-making roles. These include discrimination and harassment based on sexual orientation, ethnicity,

		<p>universities - public (large, small), private, and public-private - were chosen randomly for the research. The study sample was drawn from eleven faculties and institutes within each university, except for the small public university where all women staff were included due to their limited number. The central cluster was chosen at random,</p>		<p>race, and religion in the workplace. Additionally, the prevailing culture in many workplaces and the absence of family-friendly policies hinder women's progress. Gender-based stereotypes, discrimination, sexual harassment, and attitudinal and organisational biases, further compound the issue.</p>
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		<p>consisting of four districts. Lahore, specifically, was deliberately selected due to the presence of 22 public and 21 private universities in Punjab. Notably, Lahore alone housed 12 public and 16 private universities.</p>		
<p>Herri et al. (2016) Indonesia</p>	<p>Perceived Barriers toward Women Participation in Managerial Positions in Higher Education Institution (Evidence from Indonesia)</p>	<p>The study included 11 lecturers who were chosen as representatives from various positions such as vice Rector, Dean, vice Dean, and head of department across all</p>	<p>Personality factors, Socio-cultural factors, and Institutional factors</p>	

		faculties at Andalas University. Qualitative study & in-depth interview		
Ademe & Singh 2015 Ethiopia	Factors Affecting Women's Participation in Leadership and Management in Selected Public Higher Education institutions in Amhara Region, Ethiopia	Three Universities included Bahirdar, Gondar, and Debremarkos. Questionnaire, in-depth interview and document analysis Survey data was gathered from a total of 414 academic staff (321 males and 93 females) 30 women who have administration experience	Women face significant obstacles in participating in decision-making, including stereotyping, patriarchal systems, a lack of support at work, and lower academic qualifications. These barriers hinder their ability to contribute effectively to the decision-making and limit their opportunities for advancement in leadership roles.	Women face exclusion and isolation from academic affairs and decisions that impact them. Despite women playing a crucial role in society through managing social activities, they do not reap the benefits of their efforts and experience marginalisation in political, economic, social, and cultural aspects. Therefore, it is crucial to implement ambitious

				<p>interventions to address gender disparity in leadership. This can be achieved by promoting and empowering women in decision-making processes systematically, to reduce the existing gap, as women play a significant role in society</p>
<p>Hora (2014) Ethiopia</p>	<p>Factors that affect Women Participation in Leadership and Decision Making Position</p>	<p>The probability and nonprobability sampling methods - simple random sampling (specifically lottery method to identify the first respondent out of the first 4th s), systematic sampling</p>	<p>The lack of women's representation and participation has been attributed to several factors and constraints namely organisational structures, society's negative attitudes towards women's participation and the</p>	<p>It was concluded that women are not only kept away from higher decision-making positions, but also from access to higher education which makes them develop skills, and capacitates them with managerial</p>

		<p>method and purposive sampling 23 public institutions of Bedele Town Sample 357 Quantitative study</p>	<p>existing expectations of traditional and cultural roles for women. women's capacity to participate in decision-making roles is restricted due to overburden of family responsibilities , cultural expectations and stereotyping</p>	<p>decision-making techniques, helps them develop confidence in holding decision-making positions. recommendation Women's exclusion from the decision-making processes in public decision-making positions should be an issue, which can no longer be ignored. If at one point people saw public decision-making positions as a male domain, this alleged grounds can not be continued any longer.</p>
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7. Results and discussion

Three key factors were discovered when examining the pertinent literature on the obstacles that contribute to the underrepresentation of women in decision-making roles within higher education namely personality factors, socio-cultural factors, and institutional factors as presented in Table 2. The analysis revealed that these key factors can be grouped into two general factors namely external and internal factors. External factors are defined as outside influences that can become obstacles for women and internal factors refer to the personal way of thinking, behaviour, and attitude of women that might impact their decisions. Women's personalities and low educational status were identified as internal factors, while socio-cultural and institutional factors were identified as external factors.

7.1 Internal factors

Internal factors delve into women's self-perception, and confidence levels when it comes to decision-making processes, which can significantly impact their outcomes and achievements in various spheres of life.

7.1.1 Personal barriers (competencies factors)

According to Herri et al. (2016), the underrepresentation of women in decision-making positions can be attributed to a range of psychosocial elements, encompassing personality characteristics, attitudes, and behavioural skills. Among these individual factors are issues like diminished self-assurance and self-belief, restricted professional ambitions within managerial roles, absence of drive and determination to tackle obstacles for career progression, the stereotype of women being less capable in leadership roles, perceived as less assertive, emotionally fragile, and deficient in crisis management abilities (Herri et al., 2016).

7.1.2 Low educational status

Another obstacle faced by women in their decision-making activity was attributed to their low educational status (Tsehay, 2020; Ademe & Singh, 2015). This implies that women with limited educational qualifications encountered difficulties in making informed choices and exercising their decision-making power. The study conducted by Nyoni and He (2019) further supports this notion, emphasising the significance of educational qualifications in empowering women to make effective decisions.

7.1.3 Detrimental effects of gender stereotypes

According to Rizwana and Schmiede (2017), the initial factor highlighted the lack of leadership qualities in women, suggesting that they do not align with the traditional image of strong, decisive male leaders. This absence of assertiveness and decision-making power often results in women being perceived as competent but not likeable as leaders or representatives within organisations (Rizwana & Schmiede 2017).

Moreover, in a study conducted by Tsehay (2020), it was discovered that women face significant challenges in their decision-making activity, primarily stemming from feelings of inefficacy and lack of motivation. These findings shed light on the psychological barriers that women encounter when making important choices. The feeling of inefficacy refers to a sense of doubt or uncertainty in one's ability to make effective decisions, which can undermine a woman's confidence in her decision-making skills. Additionally, the lack of motivation can hinder women from taking initiative and actively participating in decision-making processes.

Rizwana and Schmiede (2017) have identified similar patterns, indicating that women who display assertive and masculine traits at work may be viewed as competent but unlikable, whereas those who exhibit more feminine characteristics may be seen as likeable but incompetent. These stereotypes contribute to the segregation of men and women into specific career paths, with women often being steered towards roles that are perceived as nurturing and compassionate rather than positions requiring strong decision-making abilities (Rizwana & Schmiede, 2017).

The research conducted by Hora (2014) delves into the detrimental effects of gender stereotypes on women's perceived competence and assertiveness, ultimately hindering their credibility and limiting their chances of attaining decision-making roles. These stereotypes perpetuate the notion that women are inherently less capable and authoritative than men, leading to biases in the workplace that disadvantage women in terms of career advancement and recognition for their skills and abilities.

7.2 External factors

External factors encompass socio-cultural barriers (societal norms and cultural expectations), and institutional policies that may restrict women's opportunities and choices.

7.2.1 Socio-cultural barriers (stereotypes)

The development of women's leadership is influenced by social and cultural beliefs, values, and attitudes. This research pinpointed two obstacles within the sociocultural realm namely the balance between work and personal life and attitudes towards women (Adamu, 2023).

a) Excessive family burden

Historically, women have been linked to parenting and caregiving, while men have been associated with paid employment and managerial positions in the public and industrial sectors. The ability of women to engage in decision-making roles is limited by the excessive burden of family obligations, societal expectations, and gender stereotypes, as highlighted in the study by Hora (2014) and Nyoni and He (2019). These factors create barriers for women to take on decision-making positions within institutions. Family responsibilities such as childcare and household duties often fall disproportionately on women, leaving them with less time and energy to focus on their professional development. Adamu (2023) commented that women face the challenge of prioritising their families over their careers due to gender-based division of labour and social expectations. This includes decision-making roles, as women are often burdened with the primary responsibility of caring for their families, particularly their children, irrespective of their religious, social, or academic backgrounds (Adamu, 2023). The gender-based division of labour plays a crucial role in shaping the challenges faced by women in balancing their family and career responsibilities. Traditional gender roles assign women the primary responsibility of caregiving, while men are expected to be the primary breadwinners. This division of labour not only limits women's career prospects but also reinforces societal expectations that prioritise family over career. As a result, women often find themselves having to make difficult decisions and sacrifices, such as reducing their working hours, taking on lower-paying jobs, or even leaving the workforce altogether, to fulfil their familial obligations.

b) Negative attitudes towards women

The prevailing negative attitudes of society towards women's participation, coupled with the enduring expectations of traditional and cultural roles assigned to women, are significant factors (Hora, 2014). Cultural norms and expectations may dictate that women prioritise their families over their careers, further hindering their advancement in decision-making roles (Hora, 2014). In the same way, Herri et al. (2016) found that women often prioritise family responsibilities over work commitments, as they have the responsibility of caring for their children. Consequently, they may find themselves dedicating less time and losing interest in their jobs (Herri et al., 2016). Tsehay (2020) argues that women faced numerous challenges that hindered their ability to make decisions; these include the burden of societal expectations and responsibilities placed on women, regressive socio-cultural beliefs and practices that limited their autonomy, and a pervasive sense of discrimination against women.

The study Rizwana and Schmiede (2017) discovered that the patriarchal structure can contribute to women occupying lower positions in the hierarchy, irrespective of their qualifications and education. It was observed that institutions tend to favour male leaders. Gender inequality in decision-making is significantly impacted by gender stereotyping, particularly in the form of underestimating the capabilities of female leaders in comparison to their male counterparts (Xiang et al., 2017). The prevailing negative attitudes within social circles contribute to the perception that women are unfit for decision roles, primarily due to the belief that males possess and display the innate talent required for effective decision-making (Adamu, 2023). Additionally, society tends to prioritise certain professions as safer and more suitable for women, which in turn limits their opportunities for upward mobility in the hierarchy (Rizwana & Schmiede, 2017). Ademe and Singh (2015) add that women face significant obstacles in participating in decision-making, including patriarchal systems, and a lack of support at work. These barriers hinder their ability to contribute effectively to decision-making and limit their opportunities for advancement in leadership roles (Ademe & Singh, 2015). Furthermore, the study conducted by Nyoni and He (2019) delved into the societal influences that impact individuals, particularly in terms of lack of social support, male dominance, and gender stereotypes. These factors were found to

have significant implications on various aspects of people's lives, shaping their behaviours, beliefs, and opportunities.

7.2.2 Institutional or organisational barriers

The lack of women's representation and participation has been attributed to several factors and constraints namely organisational or institutional structures (Hora, 2014).

a) Discriminatory appointment and promotion practices

Various structural factors contribute to the challenges faced by women in achieving equal representation in decision-making positions. These factors include discriminatory appointment and promotion practices, as well as male opposition to women taking on managerial roles (Herri et al., 2016). Additionally, the lack of policies and legislation aimed at promoting women's participation in leadership roles further exacerbates the issue. Moreover, the limited opportunities for leadership training and the showcasing of competence also play a role in hindering women's advancement in the workplace. These structural barriers highlight the need for comprehensive strategies to address gender inequality in decision-making positions. (Herri et al., 2016).

The hierarchical structure within organisations tends to favour men and perpetuate gender inequalities, making it difficult for women to break through the glass ceiling and reach executive positions (Rizwana & Schmiede 2017). Moreover, the power dynamics inherent in hierarchical structures can create environments where women are vulnerable to harassment and discrimination, making it harder for them to assert themselves and succeed in male-dominated industries (Rizwana & Schmiede 2017).

b) Exclusion and isolation of women from academic affairs

Ademe and Singh (2015) observe that women, in specific cases, might encounter exclusion and isolation within academic settings, where decisions affecting them are made without their input. Furthermore, the existing affirmative action measures have not fully realised their intended goals, largely due to misunderstandings and misinterpretations surrounding them. Despite women's significant contributions to society by overseeing social functions, they often do not receive the recognition and rewards commensurate with their efforts, leading to their marginalisation across various spheres such as politics, economics, social interactions, and cultural domains (Ademe & Singh, 2015).

c) Insufficient institutional support

The low access to decision-making positions highlighted by Tsehay (2020) underscores the systemic barriers that women face in climbing the corporate ladder and breaking through the glass ceiling. Without equal opportunities to assume leadership roles, women are often relegated to lower-level positions, preventing them from fully utilising their skills and expertise in decision-making capacities.

Moreover, the insufficient institutional support mentioned by Tsehay (2020) further exacerbates the challenges faced by women in decision-making activities. Without the necessary resources, mentorship, and advocacy within their organisations, women may struggle to navigate the complexities of leadership roles and make meaningful contributions to strategic decision-making processes. This lack of support can ultimately hinder women's professional growth and limit their ability to effect positive change within their organisations.

d) Gender-based discrimination within institutions

Gender-based discrimination against women is prevalent within various institutions, manifesting in job segregation, wage gaps, sexual harassment, restricted career progression avenues, such as insufficient mentorship and biased performance assessments, and a lack of promotional opportunities (Nyoni & He, 2019). These discriminatory practices not only hinder women's professional growth and development but also perpetuate systemic inequalities that disadvantage women in the workplace. Job segregation refers to the practice of steering women into certain roles or industries based on traditional gender norms, limiting their access to higher-paying or more prestigious positions (Birkelund, Lancee, Larsen, Polavieja, Radl, Yemane, 2022). Wage disparities further compound the issue, with women often earning less than their male counterparts for the same work, despite possessing similar qualifications and experience. Sexual harassment is another form of gender-based discrimination that women frequently encounter in institutional settings, creating hostile work environments and undermining their sense of safety and well-being. Additionally, the lack of adequate mentorship and biased performance evaluations can impede women's career advancement by depriving them of the guidance and recognition needed to progress within their organisations.

Figure 2 illustrates an analytical framework that shows the obstacles leading to the lack of women in decision making positions within higher education.

Figure 2: An analytical framework depicting the barriers contributing to the underrepresentation of women in decision-making roles in higher education

8. Implications

The ability of women to engage in decision-making roles is limited by the excessive burden of family obligations, societal expectations, and gender stereotypes. The findings suggest that addressing these systemic barriers is crucial in promoting gender equality in leadership. Organisations need to implement policies that support work-life balance, provide equal opportunities for career advancement, and challenge traditional gender roles. By creating a more inclusive and supportive work environment, women can be empowered to overcome these obstacles and thrive in decision-making positions. Furthermore, raising awareness about

unconscious biases and stereotypes can help to change perceptions about women's leadership abilities and capabilities. Ultimately, breaking down these barriers is essential for achieving greater diversity and representation of women in leadership roles.

It was revealed that women face diminished self-assurance and self-belief, restricted professional ambitions within managerial roles, absence of drive and determination to tackle obstacles for career progression, the stereotype of women being less capable in leadership roles, perceived as less assertive, emotionally fragile, and deficient in crisis management abilities. The presence of such psycho-social barriers underscores the need for targeted interventions and support systems to empower women to overcome these challenges and ascend to decision-making positions. By addressing these underlying issues, organisations can foster a more inclusive and diverse leadership landscape, benefiting from a wider range of perspectives and talents. Furthermore, understanding the nuances of these psycho-social factors can inform the development of tailored leadership development programs and initiatives aimed at bridging the gender gap in leadership. By recognising and addressing the specific challenges faced by women in leadership roles, organisations can create a more conducive environment for female leaders to thrive and excel. Ultimately, by dismantling these barriers, this study paves the way for a more equitable and representative leadership landscape in higher education.

By shedding light on the impact of gender stereotypes on women's professional lives, the study highlights the need for institutions to address and challenge these harmful beliefs to create a more equitable and inclusive work environment. Leaders and decision-makers should recognise the pervasive nature of gender biases and take proactive steps to mitigate their influence on hiring, promotion, and evaluation processes. Additionally, the findings underscore the importance of promoting diversity and inclusion initiatives that empower women to break free from the constraints of stereotypes and fulfil their leadership potential. By fostering a culture that values and respects the contributions of all individuals, regardless of gender, institutions can harness the full range of talent and perspectives that women bring to the table, ultimately leading to better decision-making and overall success.

The social expectations placed on women further exacerbate the challenge of prioritising family over career. Society often expects women to be the primary caregivers, nurturing and tending to the needs of their families. The implications of these findings are far-reaching and call for a comprehensive examination of the gender-based division of labour and societal expectations. It is crucial to challenge and dismantle the traditional gender roles that perpetuate the burden on women to prioritise their families over their careers. This can be achieved through policy changes, workplace support systems, and cultural shifts that promote gender equality and work-life balance. By addressing these underlying factors, society can create an environment where women are not forced to choose between their families and their careers but rather have the opportunity to thrive in both domains.

Low educational status and lack of qualifications were the main challenges to women's decision-making activity. These findings shed light on the critical role of education in enhancing women's decision-making abilities and emphasise the need for initiatives that promote educational opportunities for women to overcome these challenges. Moreover, the dearth of promotional prospects for women reflects a systemic bias that favours men in decision-making positions, perpetuating a cycle of inequality that limits women's access to top-tier roles and decision-making positions. Addressing these forms of gender-based discrimination requires a comprehensive approach that involves policy changes, cultural shifts, and organisational reforms to create more inclusive and equitable workplaces for women.

The implications of these findings are noteworthy as they highlight the need for interventions and support systems that address the underlying factors contributing to women's feelings of inefficacy and lack of motivation. By addressing these challenges, it is possible to empower women and enhance their decision-making capabilities. Strategies such as providing mentorship programs, building self-confidence through skill development workshops, and fostering a supportive environment can play a crucial role in overcoming these barriers. Moreover, organisations and policymakers should recognise the importance of gender equality and inclusivity in decision-making processes to ensure that women's voices are heard and their perspectives are taken into account. Moreover, these findings have broader societal implications. Women's decision-making power is

crucial not only for their personal lives but also for the overall development and progress of societies. When women are empowered to make informed decisions, they can contribute to positive social change, economic growth, and improved well-being for themselves and their communities. Therefore, it is imperative to address the challenges identified in this study and create an enabling environment that supports and encourages women's active participation in decision-making processes. By doing so, we can foster gender equality and create a more inclusive society.

9. Recommendations

To rectify this imbalance in the representation of women in decision-making positions in higher education, it is recommended to implement proactive measures that promote gender equity and inclusivity in higher education leadership. This entails creating supportive environments that encourage women's participation, dismantling systemic barriers, and fostering mentorship and professional development opportunities for aspiring female leaders. Additionally, raising awareness about the importance of gender diversity in decision-making and challenging societal norms and biases can contribute to a more inclusive and equitable higher education landscape.

10. Conclusion

These findings shed light on the complex interplay of internal and external factors that contribute to the scarcity of women in decision-making roles. In conclusion, decision-making in higher education should not be confined to a specific gender, and it is crucial to recognise the underrepresentation of women in these roles. The existing body of research highlights the need to address this issue globally. By actively promoting gender equity and inclusivity, higher education institutions can foster a more diverse and effective decision-making process that reflects the varied perspectives and experiences of all individuals involved.

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